

Studies in Acetyl Bromide as a Polar Solvent. Part II. Solvolytic Reactions in Acetyl Bromide

Ram Chand Paul, Sarjit Singh Sandhu, and Jagtar Singh Bassi

Solvolytic reactions of a number of oxides, nitrates, nitrites, carbonates, and acetates has been studied quantitatively in acetyl bromide. A mechanism for solvolysis of these compounds, based on ionisation of acetyl bromide into acetyl cation and bromide ions, has been proposed.

In continuation of studies on acetyl bromide, solvolytic reactions providing useful information as to the polar nature of a solvent have been investigated. Solvolysis of oxides, nitrates, carbonates, acetates, etc. in acetyl bromide has been described. Selenium dioxide, which interacts vigorously with acetyl chloride under ordinary conditions to yield selenium tetrachloride along with a dark-coloured liquid (Singh, Paul and Sandhu, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 319), reacts with ice-cooled acetyl bromide to furnish a light yellow product in low yield. Analysis of this product, which decomposes slowly, confirms formation of selenium tetrabromide. The low yield of the product may be ascribed to side reactions involving selenium tetrabromide and acetic anhydride and to its high solubility in acetyl bromide (Morgan and Drew, *ibid.*, 1925, 531).

Stannic oxide reacts with acetyl bromide to form stannic bromide, which goes into solution. Formation of stannic bromide in solution has been confirmed by isolating its complex with tetraethylammonium bromide, the results of analysis of which are recorded in Table I.

Bismuth trioxide reacts with acetyl bromide to form a red solid, analysis of which leads to the composition $\text{BiBr}_3 \cdot 2(\text{CH}_3\text{CO})_2\text{O}$. Formation of similar addition compounds between acetic anhydride and metal chlorides has already been reported (Singh *et al.*, *loc.cit.*).

Cadmium oxide on refluxing with acetyl bromide for 8 hours yields a dirty white compound, which has been found to be a solvate of cadmium bromide with acetyl bromide. This solvate on heating to 160° yields almost pure cadmium bromide.

Calcium oxide and magnesium oxide are not completely solvolyzed by acetyl bromide even on refluxing the mixture for a longer period as compared to the other oxides. Conversion of calcium oxide to bromide appears to be higher than that of magnesium oxide.

The mechanism of reactions between acetyl bromide and the oxides may be explained on the basis of an analogy with similar reactions in acetyl chloride (Singh *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). According to the views of McGookin and Page (*ibid.*, 1951, 2769) it is suggested that a primary reaction between an oxide and acetyl bromide results in the formation of an addition compound, which subsequently rearranges itself to produce acetic anhydride and metallic bromide.

In certain cases, e.g., bismuth oxide, calcium oxide, and magnesium oxide, an addition compound of acetic anhydride and metallic bromide is, however, obtained as the resultant product.

Solvolytic reaction of silver nitrate has been reported in acetyl chloride (Singh *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). Acetyl bromide and finely powdered silver nitrate react vigorously at room temperature to yield silver bromide with copious evolution of brown fumes of the oxides of nitrogen. To ensure completion of this reaction, the mixture was refluxed for two hours. Acetyl bromide, as already proposed in Part I (this issue, p. 81), ionises as :

The mode of solvolytic reaction between acetyl bromide and silver nitrate can be expressed as :

Acetyl nitrate formed during this reaction decomposes to nitrogen dioxide or nitrosyl bromide and other products in presence of excess of acetyl bromide (Diels and Okada, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 3333).

Nitrates of barium and lead also yield the corresponding bromides ; the mode of the reaction may be explained on similar grounds.

Carbonates of lithium, copper, and cadmium are completely solvolysed with formation of the corresponding bromides. Lithium and copper carbonates yield anhydrous bromides, but cadmium carbonate, just like its oxide, produces a solvate of the formula $\text{CdBr}_2 \cdot \frac{1}{2}\text{CH}_3\text{COBr}$ while solvolysis of magnesium carbonate indicates conversion of the carbonate into the pure bromide with the oxide present as an impurity. The oxide undergoes solvolysis very slowly and its presence in the carbonate as an impurity may be the cause of incomplete solvolysis of magnesium carbonate. Absence of unsolvolyed carbonate has been proved by the non-existence of carbonate ions in the solvolysed product. The mode of solvolysis of carbonates, as exemplified by that of copper carbonate, is shown as :

Formation of insoluble copper bromide and unstable acetyl carbonate, the latter decomposing to acetic anhydride and carbon dioxide, favours the forward reaction :

A study of the solvolysis of potassium nitrite and sodium sulphite also indicates complete conversion of these salts to bromides ; the mode of their reaction may be expressed as :

Acetyl nitrite may decompose as :

The interaction of sodium sulphite and acetyl bromide may be represented by the equations :

Acetyl sulphite may decompose further to Ac_2O and SO_2 :

Sodium and uranyl acetates form the corresponding bromides. Uranyl bromide is, however, associated with acetic anhydride, which is formed as a byproduct during solvolysis. A similar compound has been obtained during solvolysis of uranium trioxide in acetyl chloride (Chretien and Oeschoel, *Compt. rend.*, 1938, 206, 254). Solvolysis of acetates can be expressed by taking into consideration the reaction between sodium acetate and acetyl bromide, expressed as :

Formation of insoluble sodium bromide and undissociated acetic anhydride favours the forward reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

Partial solvolysis of inorganic compounds was effected by mixing the substances with acetyl bromide in a sealed ampoule and keeping them at room temperature. In certain cases solvolysis went to completion even at room temperature; but in other cases for complete or maximum solvolysis, the following procedure was followed.

The well-dried solid (3-4 g.) was added to acetyl bromide (20-30 c.c.) in a 100 c.c. standard joint flask equipped with a water condenser and a guard tube to avoid moisture. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for a time depending on the nature of the compound; acetyl bromide was replenished occasionally as required. The mixture was filtered in a dry atmosphere; the solid was washed with a dry inert solvent and put in *vacuo* to evaporate excess of the solvent, and then analysed.

The reaction of selenium dioxide with acetyl bromide, which was violent, was performed at 0°; contents were filtered after keeping the mixture for 2 hours in an ice bath. The solid was washed with dry petroleum ether (60-80°) and analysed as such because even under vacuum it showed decomposition. It is very much susceptible to moisture.

SnBr_4 , formed on solvolysis of stannic oxide, remained in the solution of acetyl bromide. This was isolated as a complex by treating this solution with a tetraethylammonium bromide solution. The complex was analysed. The results prove that the complex is of the formula $(\text{Et}_4\text{N})_2\text{SnBr}_6$, which can only be formed from SnBr_4 . [Found: Br, 54.83; Sn, 13.97. $(\text{Et}_4\text{N})_2\text{SnBr}_6$ requires Br, 55.89; Sn, 13.82%].

TABLE I

Compound.	Solvolyzed product.	Colour.	Temp.	Time of reflux.	Found.	Calc.
SeO ₂	SeBr ₄	Red	0°	2 hrs.	Br: 65.13 Se: 17.77	80.20 19.79
SnO ₂	SnBr ₄	Red soln.	Reflux	4	..	..
Bi ₂ O ₃	BiBr ₃ .2Ac ₂ O	Red	..	4	Br: 35.12 Bi: 31.80	36.77 32.15
CdO	CdBr ₂ .½AcBr	Dirty white	..	8	Br: 58.16 Cd: 33.71	59.88 33.63
	CdBr ₂	White	..	..	Br: 56.32 Cd: 38.40	58.74 41.25
CaO	CaO.3 CaBr ₂ . Ac ₂ O	..	..	15	Br: 47.01 Ca: 15.92	49.89 16.63
MgO	2MgO.MgBr ₂ .3Ac ₂ O	..	..	10	Br: 27.34 Mg: 12.68	28.06 12.06
AgNO ₃	AgBr	Yellow	..	2	Br: 42.21 Ag: 56.94	42.55 57.44
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	BaBr ₂	White	..	8	Br: 52.70 Ba: 56.94	53.87 57.44
Pb(NO ₃) ₂	PbBr ₂	Grey	..	10	Br: 42.56 Pb: 56.57	43.59 56.40
CuCO ₃	CuBr ₂	Black	..	6	Br: 69.21 Cu: 29.92	71.75 28.24
Li ₂ CO ₃	LiBr	White	..	25	Br: 91.40	91.95
CdCO ₃	CdBr ₂ .½AcBr	Dirty white	..	8	Br: 59.20 Cd: 32.83	59.88 33.63
*MgCO ₃	xMgO.yMgBr ₂ .zAc ₂ O	White	..	8	Br: 28.98 Mg: 10.71	
KNO ₃	KBr	..	..	6	Br: 58.00	57.22
Na ₂ CO ₃	NaBr	..	..	8	Br: 78.80	77.66
CH ₃ COONa	NaBr	..	..	6	Br: 77.32	77.66
UO ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂	UO ₂ Br ₂ .2Ac ₂ O	Black	..	2	Br: 27.10 U: 35.99	25.27 37.44

* The product obtained after solvolysis gave no test for carbonate ions, showing thereby that magnesium carbonate had fully been solvolysed. But analysis showed that magnesium was in excess of that required for any formula of MgBr₂.(CH₃CO)₂O and CH₃COBr, indicating the presence of some impurity of magnesium oxide in the product.